

APPLICATION OF CONJOINT ANALYSIS IN NEW PRODUCT DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract: *Conjoint analysis is concerned with the measurement of psychological judgment, such as customer preferences. The theoretical development of this analysis in the behavioral science and its adoption to marketing is of recent origin. Now, an interesting extension of this methodology is its application to the design of “optimal” products and product lines. It makes use of Design Of Experiments (DOE) for collection and analysis of product data. In this study, conjoint analysis is used to evaluate and test simultaneously multiple concepts of the rear-view mirror of an auto-rickshaw. The various attributes, their levels and customer preference of these attributes were gathered by an extensive interaction with the users (auto drivers). Prototypes were built for different combination of attributes and attribute levels and tested for customer satisfaction. Results were analyzed to determine optimal attribute levels that can give highest customer satisfaction. It is demonstrated that conjoint analysis can be effectively used in the evaluation and testing of multiple concepts simultaneously and to determine the optimal values of design attributes, which can give higher customer satisfaction.*

Key words: *QFD, Conjoint Analysis, Product Design, DOE.*

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Product development is an interdisciplinary activity requiring contributions from nearly all the functions of an enterprise; however, three functions are almost always central to a product development project i.e. marketing, design and manufacturing. A product development project is a sequence of steps or activities, which an enterprise employs to conceive, design and commercialize a product [1]. To remain competitive, an enterprise must design products and services that meet or exceed customer

expectations. However, it is impossible to remain cost competitive and offer every feature desired by customers. Therefore marketing, design and manufacturing functions need to work together for the success of the product [2].

Product development engineers and quality experts have tended to use Quality Function Deployment (QFD) to translate customer needs into product design characteristics [2]. It is typically carried out by a cross-functional team of individual who have been charged with responsibility for developing a

new product, service or process or for refining an existing one. Proponents of QFD assert that QFD has helped them reduce start-up costs, design time and cost; increase product quality and customer satisfaction; improve communication and cooperation between different functional areas; and gain market share. Others have found either a more mixed record on improvements in time, cost and quality, problems associated with the complexity generated by the process, or problems optimizing product design. Many still report that they find the process unbearably time-consuming [3]. Application of QFD requires a change in organizational culture [4]. Few companies reported that QFD required a significant amount of time (six years on an average) to penetrate throughout the organization and two years to systematize [4].

In any product development process it would be optimal to carry multiple product concepts into the prototyping and testing phase, and to select the best of those designs later in the process [5]. Few point out the need to consider many product concepts since only small percentage of new product ideas ultimately prove to be profitable [4]. Thus the product development team affords the flexibility to respond to market and technology shifts and may actually shorten total product development time. In short, there is a pressing need for a methodology, which can ensure fast, low-cost and parallel testing and evaluation of new product concepts [4].

Conjoint analysis is one such alternative, which is concerned with the measurement of psychological judgment, such as customer preferences. The theoretical development of this analysis in the behavioral science and its adoption to marketing is of recent origin. Now, an interesting extension of this methodology is its application to the design of “optimal” products and product lines. It makes use of Design Of Experiments (DOE) for collection and analysis of product data.

In this paper an attempt is made to demonstrate the use of Conjoint Analysis technique in product design and development. The paper is organized as follows; first, a brief overview of conjoint analysis is presented, second, methodology of conjoint analysis is adopted in carrying out multiple concept evaluation and testing of an automobile rear-view mirror (Auto-rickshaw).

2.0 CONJOINT ANALYSIS

Conjoint analysis is a technique for measuring trade-offs for analyzing survey responses concerning preferences and intentions to buy, and it is a method for simulating how consumers might react to changes in current product or to new products introduced into an existing competitive

array. Data may be collected in a variety of ways like mail survey, telephone surveys, internet based surveys as well as individual or group interview or focus group settings. It helps the measurement of psychological judgment such as consumer preferences. The objective of this method is to decompose stimuli, so that the utility of each stimulus attribute can be inferred from the respondents overall evaluation of the stimuli. Figure 1 shows the steps involved in conjoint analysis.

3.0 CASE STUDY

In this study, conjoint analysis is used to evaluate and test simultaneously multiple concepts of the rear-view mirror of an auto-rickshaw. The various attributes, their levels and customer preference of these attributes were gathered as detailed below by an extensive interaction with the users (auto drivers). Prototypes were built for different combination of attributes and attribute levels and tested for customer satisfaction. Results were analyzed to determine optimal attribute levels that can give highest customer satisfaction.

3.1 Identification of Attributes

During interaction with users it was found that the attributes listed in Table 1 predominantly influence the utility of the mirror and customer satisfaction.

Figure. 1 Steps involved in conjoint analysis

3.2 Determination of Attributes Levels

It was found that these attributes can have different values or different alternatives from the customer perception point of view. For each attributes the alternatives (levels) were determined by using certain qualitative techniques and their relative levels are given in Table 1. For example, for the material of the back cover of the mirror we have two levels; plastic or steel; for protrusion outside the auto body: 5cm or 10 cm, for the mirror pivot: side or bottom; for back cover shape: dome or flat; for clamping position: bottom or top and for size of the mirror: small, medium and large.

Table.1 Attributes and their levels

Code	Attributes	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3
A	Material for back cover	Plastic (A1)	Steel (A2)	-
B	Protrusion outside the auto body	5 cm (B1)	10 cm (B2)	-
C	Mirror pivot	Side (C1)	Bottom (C2)	-
D	Back cover shape	Dome (D1)	Flat (D2)	-
E	Clamping position	Bottom (E1)	Top (E2)	-
F	Size of the mirror	Small (F1)	Medium (F2)	Large (F3)

3.3 Determination of Attribute Combination

Based on the above attributes and attribute levels prototypes of the mirror can be built for testing and evaluation. Design Of Experiments (DOE) technique was used to determine the attribute combinations. There are six attributes (factors), five at two levels and one at three levels. If we go by conventional method of building the prototypes of the mirror based on full factorial design there would be 96 prototypes. However, by adapting a mixed fractional factorial design it is enough to build eight prototypes and carry out the testing and evaluation [6]. The combinations of the attributes in the eight prototypes are given in Table 2.

Table.2 Attribute Combinations

Run order	A	B	C	D	E	F
PT 1	A1	B2	C1	D2	E1	F1
PT 2	A1	B1	C2	D2	E2	F2
PT 3	A1	B1	C2	D1	E1	F2
PT 4	A2	B1	C1	D1	E1	F2
PT 5	A2	B2	C2	D2	E1	F3
PT 6	A2	B1	C1	D2	E2	F2
PT 7	A1	B2	C1	D1	E2	F3
PT 8	A2	B2	C2	D1	E2	F1

Legend: PT Prototype

3.4 Prototypes Building and Testing

Eight prototypes were built incorporating the attribute levels given in Table 2. The attribute nomenclature is given in Figure 2. The attribute levels are as detailed in Figure 2a. These prototypes were installed in the auto rickshaws as shown in Figure 3. Figure 3 shows the positioning of the prototype mirrors during the test ride. The prototype code can be translated as given in this example. Prototype PT2 corresponds to: plastic back cover, protruding outside the body by 5 cm, mirror pivoted at the bottom, with flat back cover, clamped to the body from top having medium sized mirror.

Figure.2 Mirror Nomenclature

Figure.2a Attribute Levels Terminology

Three users were selected, and each one of them was asked to drive the auto for a kilometer installing all the eight prototypes, one at a time. The users were asked to rank the eight prototypes and give a rating for each prototype in the scale of 0-100. Since the education level of most of the drivers is low, prop cards were also used to facilitate the ranking of the prototype. The ranking given by the customer is tabulated in Table 3.

The results were analyzed to determine the influence of each attribute and its level on customer satisfaction and are graphically represented as shown in Figure 4 and Figure 5.

Figure.3 Prototypes Installed in Auto-Rickshaws during Testing

Table.3 Results of Customer Rating

Run order	Results (Customer Rating)			Average
	C1	C2	C3	
PT 1	40	35	50	41.67
PT 2	80	75	90	81.67
PT 3	95	80	95	90.00
PT 4	55	35	55	48.33
PT 5	50	60	60	56.67
PT 6	60	40	55	51.67
PT 7	90	85	85	86.67
PT 8	10	10	15	11.67

Legend: PT Prototype, C1 Response of user 1, C2 Response of user 2 and C3 Response of user 3.

3.5 Analysis of Results

In Figure 4 and Figure 5 the mean of the customer rating of the prototype corresponding to different levels of attributes are plotted. In the case of back cover, plastic corresponds to level 1 and steel corresponds to level 2. The customer satisfaction / rating for plastic cover is 75, where as for steel back cover is 42.09 as given in Figure 4. This indicates that the user is more satisfied with plastic back cover than steel back cover. Similarly the customer rating for the other attributes B, C, D and E can be

obtained from Figure 4. Figure 5 gives similar ratings for attribute F at three levels. From the above it is evident that the customer will have more satisfaction at A1-B1-C2-D1-E1-F3 levels of the attributes.

Figure.4 Customer rating vs attribute levels (Two level attributes)

Figure.5 Customer rating vs attribute levels (Three level attribute)

It can be concluded that a mirror with attribute levels A1-B1-C2-D1-E1-F3 gives the maximum customer satisfaction. Thus a plane mirror of size (14 cm x 24 cm) with plastic back cover which protrudes outside the body only by 5 cm pivoted at the bottom, having dome shaped back cover clamped to the body from the bottom, gives maximum customer satisfaction.

4.0 CONCLUSION

The above case study demonstrates that conjoint analysis can be effectively used in the evaluation and testing of multiple concepts simultaneously and to determine the optimal values of design attributes, which can give higher customer satisfaction.

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